

DEVELOPING SUSTAINABLE TOURISM LOGISTICS WITH ENHANCING ECO-TOURISM DESTINATIONS IN EASTERN ECONOMIC CORRIDOR (EEC), THAILAND

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Abstract

After covid pandemic, tourism industry faces with huge challenge. Tourism has become a significant industry to drive Thailand's economy growth. Under Thai government policy, Eastern Economic Corridor (EEC), has been promoted, as special economic zone to attract global trade and investment. The ECC integrates Chonburi, Rayong, Chachoengsao provinces to develop industrial and economic zones. There are many beautiful and fantastic tourism destinations in EEC. However, the destinations lack sustainable development and connectivity. Ever-increasing tourism has logistically created problems there related to the sufficiency of its infrastructure systems and facilities. Increasing demands negatively affect to natural resources and an escalation of environmental pollutants. Further, these problems reflect the need for providing effective logistical planning and management in tourism industry in EEC. Logistics plays an indispensable role in the tourism industry. The development of tourism logistics for creative eco-tourism requires understanding of the behaviour and needs of tourists together with designing a responsive logistics system for them. This study applies principles of logistics management to the tourism industry under the hypothesis that moving tourists from origin to destinations more efficiently and effectively. It also includes providing an effective transport networking system, would increase and support tourism in EEC. A demand forecast for tourism in next decade was statistically calculated in order to provide recommendations for the improvement of infrastructure systems and facilities. An objective is to examine demand forecast model for tourism industry in EEC. The results can be used for designing and planning infrastructure systems and facilities, including strategies for transport networks and logistics systems to support the future growth. Data are collected from secondary and primary sources, e.g., questionnaire and in-depth interview. The questionnaire is distributed to 400 potential participants, with 382 questionnaires being returned, for a 95.5 percent return rate. Validity and reliability are examined. The result shows that a time series would be an effective model for a demand forecast. It reveals that tourism destinations in EEC would double in the next decade. Effectively designed infrastructure and facilities are required to support sustainable tourism in EEC. The internet and digital platform, and artificial intelligence (AI) are strategic issues for future tourism logistics development. Further, new and fantastic tourist facilities would be increasingly developed in EEC, underscoring the need for an appropriate plan for managing environmental pollution. Finally, a reverse logistics system for garbage management would need to be effectively utilized. Rapidly increasing garbage is a problematic issue for logistics related to a sustainable, green, eco-friendly environment. This study concludes that strategic and integrated logistical management is necessary, with active participation from stakeholders.

Keywords: Tourism Logistics, Sustainable, Demand Forecast, EEC, Thailand.

1. INTRODUCTION

After covid pandemic, tourism industry faces with huge challenge. Tourism has become a significant industry to drive Thailand's economy growth. Problems and obstacles in tourism development such as Tourism image, especially Pattaya, Lack of balance in tourism

management between tourist areas , Low-quality tourist market segments Some areas of transportation and logistics infrastructure are still inconvenient, not connected to tourist attractions or are connected but have problems with standards and sufficiency and Degradation of natural resources and tourist attractions (Office of the Eastern Economic Corridor Policy Committee,2024) Under Thai government policy, Eastern Economic Corridor (EEC), has been promoted, as special economic zone to attract global trade and investment. The ECC integrates Chonburi, Rayong, Chachoengsao provinces to develop industrial and economic zones. There are many beautiful and fantastic tourism destinations in EEC. However, the destinations lack sustainable development and connectivity. Ever-increasing tourism has created problems there related to the sufficiency of its infrastructure systems and facilities. Increasing demands negatively affect to natural resources and an escalation of environmental pollutants. Further, these problems reflect the need for providing effective logistical planning and management in tourism industry in EEC.

Logistics plays an indispensable role in the tourism industry. The development of tourism logistics for creative eco-tourism requires understanding of the behavior and needs of tourists together with designing a responsive logistics system for them. This study applies principles of logistics management to the tourism industry under the hypothesis that moving tourists from origin to destinations more efficiently and effectively. It also includes providing an effective transport networking system, would increase and support tourism in EEC. A demand forecast for tourism in next decade was statistically calculated in order to provide recommendations for the improvement of infrastructure systems and facilities.

The logistics management in the tourism industry is currently recognized as a strategic tool for enhancing tourist satisfaction in relation to lower travel costs, one-stop services, other conveniences and safety. The research study (Briguglio 1995; Bryden 1973) shows that tourism industry typically fails to understand how to apply logistics concepts as well as how to put logistics strategies into action. The objective is to examine demand forecast model for tourism industry in EEC. The results can be used for designing and planning infrastructure systems and facilities, including strategies for transport networks and logistics systems to support the future growth. It also examines other logistical aspects (i.e., role of demand forecasting and managing reverse logistics system for garbage).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study reviews the literature related to the role of tourism and eco-friendly tourism to the economic growth of Thailand. It also considers the adoption of logistics planning and management in the tourism industry. Point out that logistics planning and management contributes to the success of sustainable tourism development. These sources also review definitions of logistics management as they pertain to sustainable development of tourism, but there is few research providing definition and implications of tourism logistics, and how it contributes to tourism success. (Ekkapong C., et al. 2021; Kayumovich K. O. et al. 2020). In particular, it reveals that there are research gaps in tourism logistics management in special economic zones.

Lanfant, M. F., et. al. (1995) defines tourism logistics involves the strategic planning and execution of transporting tourists and their goods seamlessly from origin to destinations to ensure efficient and sustainable travel experiences. Tourism logistics involves the planning, control, and coordination of various resources to facilitate the flow of goods, services, and information, essential for the tourism sector. (Lanfant, M. F., et. al. 1995). This field ensures that the necessary infrastructure, transportation, and support mechanisms are in place to offer a seamless travel experience for tourists. (Studysmarter, 2025) Logistics in tourism refers to the complex processes required to ensure that tourists can travel smoothly and enjoyably from their point of origin to their destination, and back. This includes several key components. (Tairova M. M. 2018). The components cover tourist attractive destination, tourist infrastructure and facilities, access tourist and smart logistics.

It is important to understand a clear and concise concept of logistics from a tourism perspective. Logistics is mostly understood in term of business industries, and there are some research studies done exclusively in relation to tourism. People typically relate logistics (Bowersox & Closs, 1996) to transportation or accommodations, particularly connecting it to aspects of physical and information flow (Butler, 1980; Theppitak, 2006). To apply logistics to tourism industry, people, or tourists, shall be considered as physical flow from one point to another, and examined in terms of lower costs, higher safety and more convenience through excellent coordination and collaboration (Bowersox & Closs, 1996).

Conlin and Baum (1995) states that there is relationship between adoption of logistics management in the tourism industry and the success of sustainable tourism development. Logistics management means moving people, or tourists, from one point to another point (Theppitak, 2006). First, tourist demand in EEC would be examined. Accuracy of demand forecasting is important for providing logistics infrastructure and facilities. This facilitates how to prepare hotels and accommodations to support targeted tourists who access in-out the EEC, how to provide sufficiently transport networks between and within locations to support sustainable tourism (see Figure 1). However, there is the gap in literature for application logistics in tourism industry. This study applies a logistical approach to the tourism industry under the hypothesis that moving tourists from an origin place to destinations in EEC more efficiently and effectively. It includes providing an effective transport networking system, would increase tourist satisfaction in EEC. Tourism is qualitatively different from the other domains within the cultural sector, as it cannot be readily classified as a sector in the traditional sense, i.e., as measured by either particular markets or industrial outputs. Therefore, it is better understood as a demand-driven, consumer-defined activity.

Logistics service business is an outsourced service business that provides logistics services to entrepreneurs. In order for a service business to maintain lower costs, responsive and competitive services, it must rely on the three marketing activities in the service triangle (Kotler,1994; Zeithaml & Bitner,2000) which consists of the relationship of business or service provider, employees and customers as the triangle of service business marketing.

Figure 1: Relationships between activities in tourism logistics

When considering the factors influencing adoption of logistics management in tourism industry, particularly, tourism in special economic zones, the literature points out the major factors are economic, political and technology.

The research (Conlin and Baum, 1995) also highlights the relationship between such factors and the adoption of logistics management, like fluctuating tourist counts and tourist satisfaction.

It concludes there is a literature gap related to the examination of issues related to adoption of logistics management (and its effectiveness) within the tourism industry, and specifically in special economic zones.

In particular, there needs to be an examination of the factors contributing to the logistics adoption phase and the factors influencing sustainable tourism development. This study therefore proposes a theoretical framework (Figure 2) derived from a previous study (Theppitak, 2006).

Figure 2: Theoretical framework of the study

Figure 2 shows the theoretical framework of variables in this study. Building a sustainable tourism industry, especially tourism in special economic zones, required widely applied logistics concept and strategies. Success of sustainable tourism development requires a high priority of importance on adoption of logistic planning. The research shows that more importance placed on the logistics planning, more effectiveness is gained for developing tourism, in term of tourist satisfaction.

A main objective is to find ways to improve tourist satisfaction. This study examines relationship between variables (X , Y , Z). It defines a degree of importance to the adoption of logistics planning and management as *an independent variable* ($X1$ and $X2$) and defining the effectiveness of logistics management to eco-tourism in EEC, in terms of tourist satisfaction (i.e., convenience, comfort and safety for transport network, infrastructure and facilities in EEC.), and return rate of tourist as *a dependent variable* ($Y1$ and $Y2$).

Furthermore, this study discovers that other influential factors, such as economic, political and technology, are significant to effective adoption of logistics management to develop or enhance eco-tourism in EEC. These influential factors are defined in the framework as *an intervening variable*, (Variable Z), which influences both the independent variable (Variable X) and the dependent variable (Variable Y). It is therefore assumed that the level of such influencing factors has a direct correlation to the degree of importance placed on the adoption of logistics management, as well as to the effectiveness of eco-tourism in EEC.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study initially conducts a literature review related to the role and patterns of eco-tourism development in special economic zones from a logistics perspective, including the examination of challenges and obstacles occurred. It also explores the use of logistics management in the tourism industry.

The objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between variables related to effective adoption of logistics management for eco-tourism in EEC, and the effectiveness for sustainable eco-friendly tourism development.

An interview technique is used jointly with questionnaire surveys in order to obtain relevant and in-depth information from tourists in EEC. To obtain the data, the study uses a sample of 400 randomly selected tourists, which includes both Thai and foreign tourists traveling in EEC. This number of face-to-face questionnaires is based on a randomly stratified sampling. Returned questionnaires are processed and run by using descriptive statistics, correlations and analysis of moment structure (AMOS). In-depth interview is analysing by content analysis. The results are jointly used to analysing and answer research questions and objectives. The rate of response is very good, with 382 respondents, or 95.5 percent of the total questionnaires. The data collection period takes three months.

3.1 Research Questions

To answer the above issues, the study defines the following questions:

1. What is the role of logistics to sustainable eco-friendly tourism development?
2. How can behaviors of tourists be used to design tourism logistics infrastructure and facilities in EEC?
3. What are factors influencing the design and implementation of tourism logistics strategy in EEC?
4. What are efficiencies and effectiveness of tourism logistics management?

3.2 Research Hypotheses

Based on these research questions, hypotheses are established in order to examine a relationship between tourism logistics planning and management and the effectiveness of improving tourism in EEC. This study therefore examines a relationship of the variables under following hypotheses.

H_1 = There is a relationship between logistics planning and tourist satisfaction.

H_2 = There is a relationship between logistics management and increasing return rate of tourists in EEC.

3.3 Population & Sampling Procedure

This study uses the number of tourists who traveled to eco-tourism in EEC during December through February 2024. 400 questionnaires are randomly distributed for the sampling. After three months, there are 385 questionnaires returned, for a response rate of 95.5 per cent.

This study also interviews 74 tourists to gain their opinions related to tourism logistics in EEC. Two pre-testing are conducted with Cronbach's alpha (α) at 0.77 and 0.79 respectively.

4. FINDING RESULTS

The survey covers demographical data related to attitudes and behaviors of tourists when travelling in EEC, including examining hypothesis.

The research implication related to transport system, logistics infrastructure and facilities are discussed.

Table 4.1: Gender of tourists

Gender	Percent
Male	54
Female	46
Total	100

Table 4.1 shows kind of respondents. Male tourists are the greatest number of respondents in the samples or 54 percent, followed by female tourists or 46 percent.

The study represents actual information for tourism in EEC and it shows that the male tourists are a major target.

Table 4.2: Aging of targeted tourists

Age (years)	Percent
13 – 20	24
21 - 28	30
29 - 36	14
37 – 44	12
45 - 52	15
Over 52	5
Total	100

Table 4.2 represents age of targeted tourists visiting in EEC. The result shows that major tourists or 30 percent had age between 21-28 years.

Secondly, 24 percent has age between 13-20 years. The figure shows that the targeted groups of tourists in EEC are now youth and mature people.

Table 4.3: Nationality of targeted tourists

Nationality	Percent
ASEAN	33
European	10
Indian	14
Russian	18
Chinese	28
Total	100

Table 4.3 shows nationality of tourists. The survey reveals that major respondents are ASEAN countries or 33 percent.

In this number consisted of Thai respondents is at 18 percent. Chinese, Russian and Indian tourists are 28, 18 and 14 percent, respectively.

Table 4.4: Educational level of respondents

Educational level	Total
Secondary	6
High school	9
Higher school	23
Bachelor	34
Higher Bachelor	28
Total	100

Table 4.4 shows educational level of tourists. The result reveals that most of respondents or 38 percent have educational level lower than bachelor degree.

Bachelor and postgraduate degree are 34 and 28 percent, respective. The result reflects to expectation level to traveling activities, lifestyles, facilities and infrastructure in EEC.

Table 4.5: Average income of respondents

Revenue per month (Baht)	Percent
Lower 5,000	8
5,000 – 10,000	10
10,001 – 15,000	13
15,001 – 20,000	20
20,001 – 25,000	32
Higher 30,000	17
Total	100

Table 4.5 represents average income of respondents. The study reveals that average income of most tourist groups or 51 percent is lower than 20,000 baht.

The greatest number or 32 percent of them has income between 20,001 – 25,000 baht. The income levels facilitate to design and develop infrastructure and facilities in EEC consistent with targeted tourists' income.

Table 4.6: Frequency of traveling to EEC. (Excluded last traveling)

Frequency of traveling in EEC. (Times)	Percent
1	14
2 – 3	23
4-5	35
More than 5	30
Total	100

Table 4.6 reveals frequency of traveling to EEC. The result shows that most of respondents or 35 percent had been traveling to EEC 4-5 times.

Secondly, 30 percent of them travels more than 5 times. As 14 percent travels only one time. This frequency of visiting to EEC reflects to expectation, perception and satisfaction of tourists when traveling to EEC.

Table 4.7: Nature of traveling

Nature of traveling	Percent
Come alone	12
Come with friends	38
Come with family	32
Come with tour/ training/ seminar	18
Total	100

Table 4.7 reveals tourist behaviors. The survey indicates that greatest number of tourists or 38 percent travels with their friends, and 32 percent with family respectively. The information facilitates for designing pattern of transport and developing infrastructure and facilities to support sustainable tourism.

Table 4.8: Number of people in tourist group

Number of persons in a group	Percent
1 – 5	34
6 – 10	25
11 – 15	14
16 – 20	19
More than 20	8
Total	100

Table 4.8 reveals number of people in tourist group. The greatest number of tourists or 34 percent identifies that their group has 1-5 tourists. 25 percent of them identifies that travelling with 6-10 tourists per group.

Table 4.9: Pattern of vehicles to EEC

Vehicle to EEC	Percent
Public transport	18
Personal car	36
Tourist bus	23
Motorcycle	8
Other (Please identify)	15
Total	100

Table 4.9 shows patterns of vehicle for traveling to EEC. The survey shows that most of tourists or 33.3 percent traveled to EEC by personal car, 23 percent of them visited by tourist bus, and 18 percent by tourist bus respectively. However, some of them identifies that they use taxi or rent cars from Bangkok to EEC.

Table 4.10: Pattern of staying overnight in EEC

Staying overnight in EEC	Percent
Yes	57
No	43
Total	100

Table 4.10 represents pattern of staying overnight in EEC. The survey shows that most of tourists or 57 percent stay overnight in EEC for long weekend or special holiday.

The tourists point out that there is convenience both infrastructure and facilities in EEC. On the other hand, 43 percent indicates that they did not stay overnight in EEC.

Table 4.11: Type of Accommodation

Type of accommodation	Percent
Hotel	38
Resort	29
Private resident	21
Others (e.g., stay with friends)	12
Total	100

Table 4.11 shows type of accommodation in EEC. The greatest number of respondents or 38 percent stay at hotels. 29 percent of them stays in resorts and 21 percent stayed at private residents. Others or 12 percent stays with local friends or relatives. This information reveals that the tourists are expecting to stay in pattern of hotels and accommodations and travelling in EEC.

Table 4.12: Summary hypothesis testing

Variable		Correlation	p-value
Independent	Dependent		
X1	Y1	0.740	0.000
Z	Y2	0.520	0.000
X2	Y2	0.715	0.000

Table 4.12 shows summary of hypothesis testing. It tested that effective adopting logistics planning in tourism industry in EEC (X_1) have relationship with improving tourist satisfaction (Y_1). Further, effective tourism logistics management (X_2) increasingly encourage and promote increasing tourists' return rate in EEC. (Y_2). Factors (i.e., economic, political and technology) has moderately relationship with encourage and promote increasing tourists' return rate in EEC. (Y_2).

The result shows that effective adopting tourism logistics planning (X_1) has strongly relationship with generating tourist satisfaction (Y_1). It also reveals that tourism logistics management (X_2) has also moderately relationship with increasingly promoting tourists' return rate to EEC. (Y_2). In term of logistics planning covers properly matching demand of tourists and services supply in EEC provinces, including organizing logistics networks (e.g., linking between seen and unseen destinations, public transport, accommodation) within the EEC.

Further, factors are reshaping a new way to work in tourism logistics. Currently, new innovative and technology (i.e., AI, Robot, software and internet) can support for analyzing potential tourist demand, route, transport and accommodations. Tourism logistics management covers how well logistics management is used to promote and enhance tourism industry in EEC, including providing reasonable costs, safety, convenience and satisfying tourist need.

Figure 3: Structural equation model (SEM) for enhancing efficiency and sustainability to tourism logistics in standardized estimate mode, after adjusting the model.

Figure 3 shows that overall factors have a relationship between variables in medium to high levels.

After having adjusted the model for the standardized estimates, the strength and direction of relationships between variables, which are re-examined and interpreted. The estimates are crucial for understanding the model's behavior and the significance of the relationships it portrays. In a well-specified and well-fitting SEM, the standardized estimates generally fall between -1 and +1. It reveals that the effectiveness and returns of tourists in EEC depend on development and improving tourist attraction, facilities, access tourist and smart logistics.

5. DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

5.1 Role of Logistics to Sustainable Eco-Friendly Tourism Development?

Using interview methods along with questionnaires also processed Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) Found that shows kind of respondents. Male tourists are the greatest number of respondents in the samples or 54 percent. Age between 21-28 years or 30 percent. ASEAN countries or 33 percent. Have educational level lower than

bachelor degree 38 percent. The study reveals that average income of most tourist groups is lower than 20,000 baht or 51 percent. Traveling to EEC 4-5 times or 35 percent. Travels with their friends or 38 percent. The greatest number of tourists identifies that their group has 1-5 tourists or 34 percent.

Traveled to EEC by personal car or 33.3 percent. Stay overnight in EEC for long weekend or special holiday or 57 percent. Stay at hotels or 38 percent.

The findings reveal relevant patterns and trends of tourism industry in EEC. It identifies that the direction for development of eco-friendly tourism in EEC. are unclear. Current development for destinations lacks continuity, connectivity and seamless. Many destinations sufficiently lack budgets, resources, and maintenance and repairs (M&R). Government agencies cannot well plan and manage their infrastructure and facilities. There are urgent needs for application of logistics management to create and develop sustainable tourism.

Theppitak (2005) states in a definition that logistics is “the process of planning, organizing and controlling the flow of physical and information from origin to the end point to increase value with less costs to satisfy all stakeholders.” Therefore, logistics in the context of tourism is defined as “the management of the flow of physical (including tourists or vehicles) and information (information related tourists, demand, transport and accommodations).”

Under the definition, tourists are being considered as “goods,” being moved from point to point. Transport system, between provinces, as well as within the island, would need to be designed to support the move of tourists in terms of lower costs, safety, comfort and convenience. Therefore, scope of tourism logistics also covers functions i.e., transport, infrastructure and facilities. (in Figure 1)

To support and foster more and better tourism in EEC, infrastructure (e.g. electricity, water and telephone) must be readily available. Also, future facilities (for all travel activities and including currently undeveloped areas) must be well planned and organized. These facilities include hotels and other accommodations, public transport, and bus stop. Proper demand forecasts of tourist behaviors and lifestyles are critical. In-depth and accurate logistics is the only proper way to prepare for future tourist accommodations, facilities and traveling activities.

Tourism logistics also includes reverse logistics activities. Reverse logistics can be defined as the management of the flow of materials or information back to a desired point. It covers the management of garbage disposal and unusable materials. In circumstance, it includes how to recover tourists who suffering or injuring to hospital.

There are many methods to manage garbage, with different costs occurring, including non-monetary costs like pollution. This study can also be used logistically to incentive and support sustainable, more eco-friendly tourism in EEC.

5.2 Behaviors of Tourists and Designing Tourism Logistics Infrastructure and Facilities in EEC

When consider importance and satisfaction levels with public transports systems between original and destinations in EEC. It shows that tourists have moderately expectation levels of service quality (e.g., convenience, safety and fee). They have satisfactory levels lower than their expectation levels. It is the main sources of dissatisfaction. This reflects that public transport, fees and safety would be considered to improve urgently.

Tourists are satisfied when their perceptions equal or above their expectations. Therefore, the gap between tourists' expectation and perception needs to be closed.

To improve public transport systems between destinations in EEC, it would improve in two ways. First, reengineering existing public transport systems by focusing on hardware (i.e., transport, infrastructure and facilities), software (i.e., information to tourists) and peopleware (i.e., training local people with service minded).

Second, new efficient and friendly environmental transport system (i.e., Solar Cell, hydrogen and EV) would be considered.

The result shows the levels of importance and satisfaction tourists have for travel destinations. Surveyed tourists reveal they have high expectation for traveling destinations in term of beauty, atmosphere, cleanliness and safety.

However, the result shows that there are some dissatisfactions with cleanliness and sanitary system, including safety of security systems in destinations.

Managing tourism logistics in term of existing destinations, is not considered only lower costs and higher services level, but it also means to manage continuity and connectivity of routes, rest area and facilities.

Tourists inform that no new destination has been built in EEC. Unseen destinations would be effectively established and promoted. Obvious and clear signs between destinations become a source of satisfier.

When considering the levels of importance and satisfaction tourists identifying related to public transport (and facilities), while travelling in EEC. This study asks the tourists to rate the public transport systems from origin to destinations in EEC, including public transport systems within a province.

Most of the tourists indicates high expectations related to availability, convenience, safety and expenses. The study reveals that they are mostly satisfied with the availability and comfort of transport systems in EEC. However, they are somewhat dissatisfied with the safety and fees of public transport systems.

When considering the public transport system within a province, tourists have high expectations for fee standardization, and comfort and availability of transport.

But they are dissatisfied to actually find a lack of fee standardization within destinations. Logistical implication would consider in a whole system, and then set fee standardized in

each destination. The difficulty is how to communicate and motivate to local people for following to same standard without their resistance and conflict.

Figure 5: Conceptual design for sustainable tourism logistics in eco-tourism in Thailand

The interesting issue for infrastructure requires for supporting tourism in EEC, it includes electricity, road, water, and telephone systems. The results reveals that most of the tourists (more than 57 percent) stay overnight in destinations. The question is that why some tourists did not stay overnight in EEC. The interviewed results shows that most of tourists identifies to unavailability and inconvenience in term of shortage, including high prices compared with earned services. They have high expectations for the costs and availability of tourism infrastructure in EEC. But they are dissatisfied with the actual fees charged for services and the availability of infrastructure. These results reflect that there is a need to think and analyse a whole system. It would start with demand forecasting future demand to provide properly infrastructure and facilities. The study examines statistical information in last five years (2021-2025) and it shows that seasonal time series would be the demand forecasting model which fits to tourism industry in EEC. New innovative tools, (i.e., AI or Algorithm) would be used to analyze and plan for logistics infrastructure and facilities. Further, one of serious problems is garbage and pollutions occurring from tourism. Now the issue is increasingly becoming serious problems to friendly environmental tourism. It needs to apply concept of effective reverse logistics for creating and enhancing sustainable, eco-friendly tourism in EEC.

In Summary, The Main Research Finding Concludes That:

- Tourism logistics planning has a strong and positive relationship to tourist satisfaction.
- Tourism logistics management has a strong and positive relationship to return rate of tourist to EEC.

- Factors (i.e., economic, political and technology) have a moderate relationship to tourist satisfaction and they influence to decision making for traveling in EEC.
- Lacking of effective demand forecast method creates problems in mismatching between supply and demand, preparing infrastructure and facilities.
- Public transport (between origin to destinations in EEC) contributes to tourism's satisfaction and success.
- The EEC currently lacks tourism logistics planning and management.
- New innovative tools, (i.e., AI, internet or algorithm) would be used to analyze and plan for logistics infrastructure and facilities.
- Garbage from tourists is increasingly becoming serious problem, it needs to design effective and efficient reverse logistics systems.
- Effective tourism logistics enhance customer satisfaction, boost local economies, and are crucial for minimizing environmental impact and maximizing resource utilization.
- Finally, it concludes that effective tourism logistics management is a key success to tourism in EEC.

6. CONCLUSION

Effective adoption of logistics planning and management for tourism industry, especially in EEC provinces, would enhance effectively to be eco-friendly tourism. It starts from understanding tourist behavior and then analyze demand forecast for next decade. The result is a starting point for effectively designing and developing sufficient and appropriate tourism infrastructure and facilities. It points out that a seasonal time series would be an appropriate model of demand forecasting. In the next decade, tourism industry in EEC would increase to twice its current level due to development of Eastern Airport City project and the High-Speed Rail Linked 3 Airport project. Today, tourists have increasingly traveled to destinations in EEC. Effective design for future infrastructure systems and facilities must support sustainable tourism in EEC. New technology (i.e., AI, internet or algorithm) is significant role for future direction of tourism logistics. Likewise, development plans for new travel destinations must include an appropriate plan for managing environmental pollution. Finally, garbage management would be effectively planned using a reverse logistics system, as rapidly increasing garbage has become a problematic issue related to the logistics of maintaining a green, eco-friendly environment. It provides valuable information for stakeholders, especially government agencies and public policy makers. Logistically planned transport management facilitates growing tourist travel to and from provinces, providing hotel, resort and residential-accommodation owners with consistently increasing demand. While it would prevent the unrestrained destruction of natural resources and environments in destinations. This study leads to the conclusion that strategic and integrated tourism logistics management is needed, with active participation from relevant stakeholders.

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